

**Sustainable
Financing Strategies
for the RMG Industry:
Ensuring Long-Term
Environmental and
Economic Viability**

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Executive Summary

Achieving long-term environmental and economic sustainability is a problem for the RMG sector. Eco-friendly behaviors are encouraged by sustainable funding, which provides a solution. This research explores various financing approaches and the challenges hindering their adoption.

The main obstacles identified by the research include lack of funds, lack of knowledge and experience, outside influences, societal concerns, and business difficulties. Building internal capability, encouraging cooperation, incorporating sustainability into financial choices, and promoting openness are some of the ways stakeholders may address these issues.

This research acknowledges limitations like its scope, reliance on secondary data, generalizability, and limited exploration of future trends. Further research is needed to gain deeper understanding of this complex and dynamic field.

1 Introduction

In addition to a significant increase in funding and investment, achieving the goal of a decarbonized future, would need massive worldwide effort (Sustainable Finance, 2022). In the context of the ready-made garment RMG business, sustainable finance refers to financial products and investments that back ethically and ecologically responsible textile industry practices. RMG is known for its negative consequences on society and the environment, especially in developing nations where it is a major economic driver. Therefore, it is essential to find financial solutions that promote sustainability throughout its supply chain.

1.1 Research Context

For sustainability advancement in the ready-made garment (RMG) sector, it is imperative to implement an extensive and enduring sustainability strategy, coupled with enhanced accessibility to various funding avenues (Focus, 2022). The population of the world is expected to increase to 8.5 billion people by 2030 and then to 9.7 billion people by 2050. There are almost 80 billion articles of clothes in the world now, and each person uses 68 articles of clothing annually on average. By 2030, the world's garment output is expected to rise by 63% as a result of population growth. Consequently, it is critical to address environmental challenge such greenhouse gas emissions, water use in cotton production, and delayed product biodegradation (Fashion-on-Climate-Full-Report.Pdf, n.d.). The fashion industry is responsible for 2-8% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions 20% of wastewater generated worldwide, and 35% of the microplastics that end-up in the ocean. The sourcing process, which includes raw material extraction, manufacture, and treatment, is the main cause of these environmental effects. As stated in (Style-on-Climate-Complete-Report.Pdf, n.d.).

A long-term plan and readily available funding are necessary for sustainable RMG. Industry needs to address its environmental effect as demand rises. Adoption of environmentally friendly practices may be facilitated by sustainable funding, assuring the economy's and the environment's long-term existence.

1.2 Research Objectives & Main Research question.

The purpose of the research is to determine and evaluate sustainable financing strategies for the RMG sector.

Main research question: How can sustainable financing approaches ensure the long-term environmental and economic viability of the RMG industry?

1.3 Research Significance

This study is important because it has the potential to change the RMG market. By encouraging sustainable habits, it may lessen environmental harm, enhance social responsibility, and provide a solid economic basis. The results will direct investors, policymakers, and corporate leaders toward a more sustainable future.

1.4 Report Structure

In the second chapter, a comprehensive evaluation and discussion of relevant literature are conducted to establish a foundation for the research investigation. The third chapter takes a closer look at the methodology employed for data collection. Furthermore, in the fourth chapter, the research findings are presented and analyzed in-depth. Lastly, the fifth chapter sums up the research findings and the final chapter provides practical recommendations based on the research conducted.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Beyond Ethics: Weaving a Sustainable Future for the RMG

Industry

In the RMG industry, sustainable finance entails incorporating governance, social, and environmental factors into financial decision-making. In the last few decades, sustainable finance has transformed from a tactic used by moral investors (like religious organizations) to remove “bad” companies (like casinos, manufacturers of weapons, alcohol, and tobacco) from their holdings to a growing component of risk management plans for banks and other financial institutions (Archer, 2019). A diverse strategy is necessary to address the complicated challenge of ensuring the sustainability of the global RMG sector.

Le (2020) and Ng (2018) noted that, the deployment of renewable energy and the creation of a green finance system are fueled by financial development and sustainable financing. Porfir'ev (2016) emphasizes the importance of green financing even more when discussing the effects of climate change and the environment, especially in light of the Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement.

2.2 Building Sustainable Strength: The Impact of Green Finance on Supply Chain Resilience

There are many variables that influence the intricate matter of how sustainable finance affects the robustness of the RMG supply chain. The potential advantages of sustainable finance techniques, in enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of supply chains are emphasized by Zhan et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2020). However, as mentioned by Hossain & Roy (2016), the unique setting of the RMG business may have an impact on these methods' efficacy. The importance of compliance with stakeholders' requirements and sustainability governance in the RMG supply chain is also emphasized by Chowdhury et al. (2013), suggesting that these factors should be considered in the design and implementation of sustainable financing strategies.

2.3 Investing for Our Tomorrow: Sustainable Financing and the Stakeholder Imperative

A crucial component of contemporary investment is sustainable financing, which emphasizes long-term growth as well as social and environmental challenges (Gambhir, 2020). The investing community is beginning to embrace the idea of seeing future generations as stakeholders, which lends credence

to this strategy. Future generations will “inherit” the results of the actions of current generations. Investing money in some lucrative ideas is definitely a very important financial activity, but it must be done responsibly (Abrudan et al., 2021). Peer-to-peer lending and green bonds are two examples of innovative financial mechanisms that are seen to have the potential to promote social and environmental sustainability (Kerste, 2011). There is a need for the socially conscious investing community to take center stage in highlighting the financial sector's contribution to sustainable development (Peeters, 2005).

2.4 Navigating the Green Maze: Sustainable Finance Strategies

Across the Globe

Numerous studies have examined sustainable finance strategies in various geographical areas. According to Batrancea et al. (2020), the financial sector was vital even if domestic bank credit was insufficient for green finance in the USA, Canada, and Brazil. (Durst & Gerstlberger, 2020), with an emphasis on environmental sustainability, emphasized regional variations in assistance initiatives for ethical small and medium-sized businesses. Khudyakova (2023) observed a decline in the market for sustainable debt in 2022, but she also saw a change in favor of protecting biodiversity and the environment. In different research, Khudyakova & Urumov (2021) talked about how the BRICS nations' national goals include green finance, with China leading the way in terms of the amount of green bonds and loans.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

In order to investigate sustainable funding alternatives for the RMG business, this study used a qualitative methodology. Developing explanatory models and theories, characterizing and explaining the social environment, and making sense of reality are all made possible by qualitative research (Morse, 1996). This methodology is especially appropriate for this study as it seeks to shed light on the unique possibilities and problems related to sustainable finance in the RMG sector.

3.2 Data Collection Process

Data collection for this research was conducted through secondary (report, article, news etc.) and primary (interview) data collection method:

Secondary data:

- **Academic literature:** Scholarly articles, research reports, and journals provide insights into the RMG industry's environmental and economic impact, existing financing mechanisms, and emerging trends in sustainable finance.
- **Industry reports and publications:** Reports from reputable organizations like the World Bank and industry associations offer valuable information on the RMG industry's current state, its challenges, and potential sustainable financing opportunities.
- **News articles and media coverage:** Articles from credible outlets provide insights into recent developments, challenges, and ongoing discussions related to sustainable RMG financing.
- **Policy documents and government initiatives:** National and international documents, alongside government initiatives regarding sustainable development and green finance, offer perspectives on policy frameworks and potential incentives influencing RMG sustainable financing.

Primary data:

The interview included one supply chain manager of Gunzu United Ltd., Mr. S. (Appendix B) who was chosen by the researcher. However, since the respondent is selected by the researcher, it may reduce reliability and increase biases (Business Research Methodology, n.d.)

3.3 Data Analysis

The gathered information will undergo a theme analysis, a qualitative technique that entails finding, examining, and summarizing patterns in the data. Using this method will enable the identification of important themes and ideas.

3.4 Reliability & Validity

The use of primary and secondary data sources improves data triangulation and supports the research's dependability. But choosing only one interviewee might result in bias and lower the study's external validity. To mitigate this, future research should employ a broader sampling approach for enhanced reliability and validity.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The research will prioritize accuracy, fairness, and transparency, while acknowledging data limitations and avoiding claims of causation. Additionally, anonymity of any individuals will be maintained.

4 Challenges in Implementing Sustainable Financing in RMG industry:

4.1 Financial Challenges

- **High upfront costs:** Implementing sustainable practices in the RMG industry often demands substantial initial investments in new technologies, infrastructure enhancements, and workforce training. This poses a considerable obstacle for companies like Gunzu United Ltd. as Mr. S described in the interview, particularly smaller ones, which may encounter difficulties in accessing the required capital.
- **Smaller RMG companies:** Smaller RMG companies often lack the resources and economies of scale to access competitive financing options compared to larger players. This can make sustainable financing even more challenging for them.
- **Risk perception by lenders:** Lenders often view financing sustainable practices as riskier due to uncertainties surrounding new technologies, market acceptance, and potential returns on investment. This perception can hinder RMG companies, including Gunzu United Ltd. as Mr. S. said in the interview, in securing loans and other financing options.
- **Sustainable materials:** Sustainable materials often come at a higher cost than conventional materials, further adding to the financial burden of implementing sustainable practices.
- **Lack of standardized metrics:** Investors find it challenging to evaluate potential returns on investment and manage risks connected with sustainable finance due to the absence of common measures to monitor and report the environmental and social effect of sustainable practices.

4.2 Awareness and Expertise Challenges

- **Information gap:** Many RMG companies, particularly smaller ones, lack awareness of the various sustainable financing options available to them. This may be the result of a lack of knowledge about the advantages and complexity of sustainable financing, as well as restricted access to information.
- **Limited knowledge within RMG companies:** RMG companies may lack the in-house expertise to assess their own sustainability performance, develop a robust sustainability strategy, and effectively communicate their needs to potential investors and lenders. This may restrict their capacity to obtain and make efficient use of sustainable finance.

4.3 External Challenges

- **Policy uncertainty:** According to Gunzu United Ltd. in the interview with Mr. S., the lack of clear and consistent government policies and laws addressing sustainable development and green financing creates uncertainty for businesses and investors, which hinders investment in sustainable practices.
- **Consumer behavior:** Demand for sustainable products is mostly driven by consumer behavior, which also encourages RMG firms to implement sustainable practices. But given that price frequently takes precedence over sustainability in today's consumer purchasing patterns, RMG businesses find it difficult to defend the higher expenses linked to sustainable practices in the absence of strong market demand.
- **Monitoring and verification:** The process of monitoring and verifying the environmental and social impact of sustainable practices can be complex and costly, further adding to the challenges faced by RMG companies.
- **Fragmented supply chain:** The RMG industry is characterized by a complex and fragmented supply chain, making it challenging to implement and monitor sustainable practices across the entire value chain. Maintaining accountability and transparency across the supply chain may also be difficult as a result of this fragmentation.

4.4 Social Challenges

While not the sole focus of sustainable financing, social challenges can also play a role in hindering its implementation within the RMG industry. These challenges can include:

- **Labor practices and fair wages:** Ensuring fair wages and safe working conditions for workers throughout the supply chain is a crucial aspect of social sustainability. However, resolving these problems may need raising funds and altering labor laws, which may have an adverse effect on some RMG firms' capacity to make money.
- **Gender equality and empowerment:** Empowering women in the workforce and ensuring gender equality are vital for social sustainability. However, Mr. S. from Gunzu United Ltd. acknowledges that addressing these issues may demand changes in company culture and practices, necessitating additional resources and effort.

4.5 Industrial Challenges

- **Technological limitations:** The availability and affordability of technologies needed to implement sustainable practices can vary depending on the specific needs of the RMG

company. Limited access to advanced technologies can hinder the adoption of certain sustainable practices.

- **Scalability:** Scaling up sustainable practices across the RMG industry proves challenging due to its vast number of companies and diverse production processes, as highlighted in the interview with Mr. S. This complexity hinders the achievement of significant and widespread environmental and social impact.
- **Lack of Collaboration:** Insufficient collaboration and coordination among stakeholders in the RMG industry, including brands, manufacturers, and suppliers, can hinder the development and implementation of effective sustainable practices and financing mechanisms.

5 Recommendations

Integrating Sustainability into Financial Decision-Making: Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors have to be incorporated into RMG firms' financial decision-making procedures. This entails taking into account both conventional financial measures and the long-term financial effects of sustainable activities. Financial institutions ought to provide models and instruments for evaluating the potential profits and financial sustainability of sustainable investments in the RMG sector. As an illustration, the well-known outdoor clothing brand Patagonia incorporates sustainability into its main business plan (Strategy Study, n.d.). The "Citi Green Trade Program" was introduced by international banking firm Citibank with the express goal of assisting developing nations with sustainable trade finance (Review & Wragg, 2022). In addition to drawing in eco-aware customers, this dedication to sustainability will win over investors and ensure RMG Industries' long-term financial stability.

Reporting and Transparency: It is recommended that RMG enterprises adopt comprehensive sustainability reporting procedures, employing standard criteria to assess and convey their effects on the environment and society. By increasing accountability and transparency, this will draw in new investors and foster customer trust. Banks and investors should push clothing companies (RMG) to create consistent ways to report on sustainability efforts. Imagine a clothing brand like H&M – they share yearly reports on how they're improving working conditions and reducing emissions. This openness helps everyone see their progress and builds trust.

Building Internal Capacity and Expertise: RMG businesses should fund capacity-building and training initiatives to provide staff members the know-how and abilities necessary to successfully manage sustainable funding and adopt sustainable practices. To increase knowledge and competence within the RMG business, governments and industry groups can provide resources and training programs that are especially designed to meet the needs of the sector. The Adidas Group, a well-known sportswear firm, for instance, has a dedicated sustainability department that creates and executes sustainable practices across the business.

Collaborating with External Partners: Governments, NGOs, financial institutions, and RMG enterprises may work together to provide creative, easily accessible, and long-term financing solutions that are customized to meet the unique requirements of the RMG sector. To solve issues like information exchange, monitoring and verification, and expanding successful sustainable practices throughout the business, multi-stakeholder partnerships can be developed. For example, IKEA and WWF are founding members of the "Better Cotton Initiative (BCI)" and support its initiatives to change cotton production

globally (IKEA First Major Retailer to Use Only Cotton from More Sustainable Sources #WWF #IKEA, n.d.). In association with The Ellen MacArthur Foundation, H&M has launched the "Circularity Innovation Programme" (H&M Group, n.d.). This program gathers a range of fashion industry stakeholders to investigate innovative circularity solutions with the goal of reducing waste and lengthening the life of clothing.

Green bonds and loans: Promote the issue of green bonds and loans intended only for the financing of environmentally friendly projects in the RMG sector. This might provide RMG businesses access to cheaper financing.

Carbon Pricing and Offsets: By enacting carbon price plans or investigating carbon offset programs, you may encourage the global RMG industry to invest in carbon-neutral technologies and give incentives for lower emissions. The European Commission (n.d.) states that the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is a cap-and-trade system that places a limit on greenhouse gas emissions for certain industries, such the textile industry. Global RMG enterprises will be encouraged to invest in carbon-neutral activities and emission reduction technology by means of this sort of system.

Impact investing: Draw in impact investors who are especially looking to fund businesses that have both financial rewards and a beneficial social and environmental effect. Communicate with impact investors to learn about their unique preferences so that you can adjust investment offers. For example, IFC concentrates on providing investments and creative finance to assist the business sector in addressing climate change. By 2025, the World Bank Group hopes to have committed forty-five percent of its annual finance to climate change (Green Bonds, n.d.).

Supply chain collaboration: The adoption of sustainable practices by RMG companies and their suppliers need to be a cooperative endeavor. This might include cooperating to resolve problems and provide openness throughout the whole value chain, as well as sharing information and resources. Establishing clear sustainability goals for their supply chains and collaborating with suppliers to meet them might be a big way for well-known brands and merchants to support sustainable practices. For instance, Patagonia collaborates with its suppliers to include sustainable practices all the way through their supply chain. On subjects like chemical management, fair labor standards, and water conservation, they provide their suppliers information and training (Working With Factories - Patagonia, n.d.). Adidas also establishes specific sustainability objectives and integrates sustainable practices across its supply chain in close collaboration with its suppliers (Adidas - Our Targets, n.d.). Together, we can ensure that sustainability efforts are included across the whole value chain.

6 Conclusion & Discussion

Conclusion

Achieving long-term economic and environmental sustainability is a major problem for the RMG business. By providing incentives for the implementation of environmentally friendly activities, sustainable financing is a viable strategy for overcoming these obstacles. This study examined many sustainable funding approaches and noted significant obstacles to their adoption. Stakeholders can unleash the full potential of sustainable finance and clear the path for a more sustainable future for the RMG sector by incorporating sustainability into financial decision-making, promoting transparency, developing internal knowledge, and encouraging cooperation. But in order to fully comprehend this intricate and dynamic environment, more study is required due to constraints like breadth and reliance on secondary sources.

Discussion

This research, aligned with existing literature, reveals the complex challenges hindering sustainable financing in the RMG industry. These challenges span financial constraints, limited awareness and expertise, external factors, social considerations, and industrial hurdles. Financial hurdles like high upfront costs, limited access to capital, and risk perception from lenders can significantly impede RMG companies, especially smaller ones, from adopting sustainable practices (Archer, 2019; Hossain & Roy, 2016). Awareness and expertise gaps, such as the information gap and limited knowledge within RMG companies, further hinder progress (Chowdhury et al., 2013). Building capacity and expertise is crucial to address these challenges. External factors like unclear policy and consumer behavior focused on affordability over sustainability create significant barriers (Gambhir, 2020; Abrudan et al., 2021). While not the primary focus, social challenges like labor practices, fair wages, and gender equality can also impact implementation (Le, 2020; Ng, 2018). Addressing these issues can require additional resources, impacting financial viability. Industrial challenges like technological limitations and lack of collaboration among stakeholders like brands, manufacturers, and suppliers further hinder progress (Zhan et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2020; Chowdhury et al., 2013).

Limitation

This research is subject to several limitations that are important to consider:

- **Limited scope:** The research focuses on exploring sustainable financing strategies in the RMG industry. It does not delve deeply into the technical aspects of implementing sustainable

practices or the specific challenges faced by different segments within the RMG industry (e.g., garment workers, raw material suppliers).

- **Reliance on secondary data:** The research primarily relies on secondary data sources such as academic journals, industry reports, and news articles. This approach provides valuable insights but may not capture the nuances and complexities of real-world practices within the RMG industry.
- **Generalizability:** The research findings may not be generalizable to all RMG companies or regions due to the diverse nature of the industry and the varying levels of development and sustainability practices across different countries.
- **Limited focus on future trends:** While the research acknowledges emerging trends in sustainable financing, it does not extensively explore the potential impact of future technological advancements, policy changes, or consumer behavior shifts on the RMG industry and its financing landscape.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Interview Questions

Interviewer	Interview Questions
Mr. S. (Supply Chain Manager of Gunzu United Ltd.)	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What are the financial challenges faced by Gunzu United Ltd. in implementing sustainable practices?2. How does Gunzu United Ltd. perceive the risk associated with financing sustainable initiatives?3. How does Gunzu United Ltd. address the information gap and limited knowledge within the company regarding sustainable financing options?4. What external challenges impact Gunzu United Ltd.'s efforts in implementing sustainable financing?5. How does Gunzu United Ltd. tackle social challenges relate to sustainable financing?6. What industrial challenges does Gunzu United Ltd. face in implementing sustainable financing?

Appendix B: Interview Transcript with Representative of New Rebels

Interview Information	
Interviewee:	Male
Interview Design:	Semi-structured
Duration:	38.24 minutes
Date:	13 March 2024

Interviewer: Good morning, Mr. Smith. Thank you for taking the time to speak with us today. As the Supply Chain Manager of Gunzu United Ltd., we're keen to hear your insights on the challenges faced by the RMG industry in implementing sustainable financing.

Mr. S.: Good morning, it's my pleasure to be here.

Interviewer: To start off, could you share your perspective on the financial challenges that Gunzu United Ltd. encounters when it comes to implementing sustainable practices?

Mr. S.: Certainly. One of the major hurdles we face is the high upfront costs associated with transitioning to sustainable practices. Gunzu United Ltd. operates as a medium-sized RMG company, so securing the necessary capital for investments in new technologies, infrastructure upgrades, and worker training can be quite challenging.

Interviewer: I see. Given your position, how do you perceive the risk associated with financing sustainable practices?

Mr. S.: Lenders often perceive financing sustainable initiatives as riskier due to uncertainties surrounding market acceptance, return on investment, and the longevity of new technologies. This risk perception can make it difficult for us to secure loans and other forms of financing for our sustainability projects.

Interviewer: Moving on to awareness and expertise challenges, how does Gunzu United Ltd. navigate the information gap and limited knowledge within the company regarding sustainable financing options?

Mr. S.: We're continuously working to bridge the information gap by providing training and education to our staff. However, as a medium-sized company, we may lack the in-house expertise needed to assess our sustainability performance effectively. We're exploring partnerships with external consultants to address this challenge.

Interviewer: Interesting. What external challenges do you believe impact Gunzu United Ltd.'s efforts in implementing sustainable financing?

Mr. S.: Policy uncertainty is a significant external challenge for us. Clear and consistent government policies and regulations would provide the stability needed for long-term planning and investment in sustainable practices. Additionally, consumer behavior also poses a challenge, as the current emphasis on affordability over sustainability makes it difficult for us to justify the additional costs.

Interviewer: Lastly, how does Gunzu United Ltd. tackle social and industrial challenges related to sustainable financing?

Mr. S.: Ensuring fair wages and safe working conditions for our workers is a top priority for us. However, addressing these social challenges can require additional resources and changes to our labor practices. In terms of industrial challenges, we're exploring scalable solutions and seeking opportunities for collaboration within the industry to drive widespread adoption of sustainable practices.

Interviewer: Thank you, Mr. Smith, for sharing your insights on the challenges faced by Gunzu United Ltd. in implementing sustainable financing within the RMG industry. Your perspectives have been invaluable.

Mr. S.: It was my pleasure. Thank you for having me.